

Improving Cold-Start Recommendations with Social-Media Trends and Reputations

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Abstract. In recommender systems, the cold-start problem is a common challenge. When a new item has no ratings, it becomes difficult to relate it to other items or users. In this paper, we address the cold-start problem and propose to leverage on social-media trends and reputations to improve the recommendation of new items. The proposed framework models the long-term reputation of actors and directors, to better characterize new movies. In addition, movies popularity are deduced from social-media trends that are related to the corresponding new movie. A principled method is then applied to infer cold-start recommendations from these social-media signals. Experiments on a realistic time-frame, covering several movie-awards events between January 2014 and March 2014, showed significant improvements over ratings-only and metadata-only based recommendations.

Keywords: *cold-start, recommendation, online reputation, sentiment analysis, social-media.*

1 Introduction

Social-media services are a preferred way for users to obtain insight into various subjects, such as restaurants, events, books and movies. The information shared through social-media services is highly relevant to assert what everyone is consuming or looking at. Its importance is clear for recommender systems, whose goal is to compute suggestions concerning products of interest. Thus, automatic systems that mine these trends and reputations across multiple social-media services are of great value in many recommendation scenarios.

In the most common scenario, user-item ratings are predicted for old items, i.e., movies that have already been rated by users. A more challenging scenario for a recommender system is the cold-start scenario: given a new item that has not been rated or commented by any user, how can we relate this item to other items or potential consumers? In this paper, we argue that information shared in social-media services, can be useful to tackle the cold-start problem in recommender systems.

Our main contribution concerns the decomposition of a new item (a movie in our case), into key components, whose reputation can be tracked over time (actors and directors). More specifically, we propose that the reputation of directors and actors obtained from textual feedback can be a quality measure for new movies. Although these

movies have not yet been rated, their directors and actors have a track record. On top of this historical data, we also leverage on more immediate data, e.g. Twitter trends, to improve the recommendations. Experiments on data captured between January 2014 and March 2014, leveraged on the reputation record of actors and directors to improve recommendations for the cold-start scenario in the movies domain.

2 Related Work

One of the main applications of media monitoring is to capture popular topics in real-time. Twitter is one of the most popular micro-blogging services, favoring real-time user communication. Many authors have proposed methods to follow trends in Twitter [1–3]. TwitterMonitor [1] is a framework that exploits co-occurrences of bursty keywords to identify real-time trends on Twitter streams. Twevent [2] is a similar framework, which incorporates Wikipedia to identify realistic events and associate captured tweets to identified events. In turn, Ozdikis et al. [3] showed that the usage of *hashtags* improves the accuracy of event detection when compared to standard word-based vector generation methods.

A similar objective which also links to media monitoring is the reputation analysis of specific entities, such as movies, celebrities, products, etc. This process enables various applications, one of which is aiding in prediction tasks. Krauss et al. [4] used sentiment analysis on the IMDb discussion boards to predict Oscar nominations by obtaining the movies with best reputation. Joshi et al. [5] explored the popularity of old movies among online critic reviews to predict opening weekend revenues for new movies, by comparing the similarity in metadata of old highly rated movies with new ones. In a similar approach, Asur et al. [6] exploited bursty keywords on Twitter streams to predict box-office revenue for new movies. Lastly, Oghina et al. [7] predicted the IMDb movie ratings by analyzing their popularity on social-media, namely YouTube and Twitter. In contrast, we use the reputation of actors and directors combined with data from Twitter streams to compute cold-start recommendations.

In some media review services such as IMDb or Metacritic, in addition to the traditional numeric ratings, users can also input feedback using textual reviews. Valuable information that is hard to represent by numeric ratings alone can be extracted from these textual reviews. To improve recommendation in the cold-start scenario, Moshfeghi et al. [8] explored the incorporation of emotions and semantic spaces. In their collaborative recommender system, information from user reviews and plot summaries is extracted in order to better describe items and users. Similarly, Jakob et al. [9] identified and clustered movie topics using movie reviews and a ratings matrix to recommend movies based on the prediction of user-topic similarity. Zhang et al. [10], obtained good results in online video recommendation with a framework that extracts a like/dislike rating from textual reviews and comments to minimize data sparsity.

A different approach was proposed by Amatriain et al. [11], where “expert” opinions were extracted from a website widely considered as a trust-worthy source (www.rotentomatoes.com). Amatriain et al. applied *k-nn* to compute the similarity between users and experts, and recommend movies according to the most similar experts.

3 Cold-Start Recommendations with Social-Media Signals

To handle the cold-start problem, we propose a framework that computes personalized recommendations by exploring the reputation of new movies, directors and actors in social-media services, namely on Twitter and IMDb. Moshfeghi et al. [8] showed that recommendation of cold-start movies performs best when considering a movie metadata and the sentiment expressed in movie reviews. Building on this idea, we represent a movie as the vector

$$m_j = (D_j, A_j, G_j, R_j, S_j), \quad (1)$$

where D_j is the set of directors, A_j is the set of participating actors, G_j is the set of corresponding genres, R_j is the set of associated user ratings and S_j is the social-media feedback inferred by a monitoring process described in section 3.2. The S_j variable is composed of the Twitter posts (or tweets) about the movie m_j as well as the reputation of its directors and actors, obtained from IMDb. As we will see, S_j will be fundamental to improve cases of cold-start recommendations where $R_j = \emptyset$.

In this scenario, users rate the movies they have watched and from this data we compute their profiles in terms of personal preferences towards directors, actors and genres. Formally, a user u_i is then represented as the vector

$$u_i = (D^i, A^i, G^i), \quad (2)$$

where D^i is the set of directors, A^i is the set of actors and G^i is the set of genres. These three sets follow the same structure and are represented as

$$D^i = \{(d_i^1, dr_i^1, df_i^1), \dots, (d_i^n, dr_i^n, df_i^n), \dots\}, \quad (3)$$

$$A^i = \{(a_i^1, ar_i^1, af_i^1), \dots, (a_i^n, ar_i^n, af_i^n), \dots\}, \quad (4)$$

$$G^i = \{(g_i^1, gr_i^1, gf_i^1), \dots, (g_i^n, gr_i^n, gf_i^n), \dots\}, \quad (5)$$

where the first element d_i^n identifies the director, dr_i^n is the average rating given by the user to the movies directed by that director and df_i^n is the number of movies directed by d_i^n that are rated by the user. The same rationale applies to A^i and G^i .

3.1 Formal Model

We start by exploring the similarity of the user profile eq. (1) and the movie profile eq. (2). This similarity is obtained by quantifying how much a user likes each aspect of the movie separately, i.e., the values \hat{d}_{ij} , \hat{a}_{ij} and \hat{g}_{ij} , and later combining them into a final similarity score.

To infer the user u_i preference towards the directors of the movie m_j , we compute the weighted average of how much the user likes each director of the movie, i.e., the weighted average of the values dr_i for each director on D_j . The weight, representing the contribution of each director rating to the average, is pondered according to the number of movies that the user rated where the director participated, i.e., each director's corresponding value df_i on the user profile D^i . The reasoning, is that a user formulates a more refined and accurate opinion about a director if he/she watches more movies from that director. Hence, we consider that directors that have been watched more times by

the user should have a stronger weight on the prediction. Let $D_{ij} = D^i \cap D_j$ be the set of the directors of movie m_j that are on the user profile D^i . The weight $w_{d_{ij}}^n$ of the n^{th} director $d_{ij} \in D_{ij}$ is then obtained by the expression

$$w_{d_{ij}}^n = \frac{df_i}{\sum_{p \in D_{ij}} df_p}, \quad (6)$$

such that $\sum_n w_{d_{ij}}^n = 1$. Considering this, the preference of user u_i towards the team of directors of the movie m_j is obtained by the expression

$$\hat{d}_{ij} = \frac{\sum_{n \in D_{ij}} dr_i^n \cdot w_{d_{ij}}^n}{|D_{ij}|}, \quad (7)$$

where $|D_{ij}|$ is the number of directors on D_{ij} . Since all director ratings dr_{ij} are values between 1 and 10, the resulting average \hat{d}_{ij} will also be a value between 1 and 10. Note that when none of the directors of movie m_j are on the user's directors set D^i , $\hat{d}_{ij} = 0$.

How much the user u_i likes the actors of the movie m_j can be obtained similarly to how \hat{d}_{ij} is obtained. Let $A_{ij} = A^i \cap A_j$ be the set of actors of movie m_j that are on the user profile A^i . Thus, the user u_i preference towards likes the actors of the movie m_j is obtained by the expression

$$\hat{a}_{ij} = \frac{\sum_{n \in A_{ij}} ar_i^n \cdot w_{a_{ij}}^n}{|A_{ij}|}, \quad (8)$$

where $|A_{ij}|$ is the number of actors on A_{ij} and w_a is the weight of the actor a . Similarly to \hat{d}_{ij} , when none of the actors of movie m_j are on the user actors A^i , $\hat{a}_{ij} = 0$. In turn, let $G_{ij} = G^i \cap G_j$ be the set of the genres of movie m_j that are on the user profile G^i . How much the user u_i likes the genres of the movie m_j is obtained by the expression

$$\hat{g}_{ij} = \frac{\sum_{n \in G_{ij}} gr_i^n \cdot w_{g_{ij}}^n}{|G_{ij}|}, \quad (9)$$

where $|G_{ij}|$ is the number of genres on G_{ij} and w_g is the weight of the genre g . Like \hat{d}_{ij} , and \hat{a}_{ij} , $0 \leq \hat{g}_{ij} \leq 10$, with 0 occurring when none of movie genres are on the user genres G^i .

The predicted rating \widehat{pr}_{ij} for user u_i and the *cold-start* movie m_j is obtained by the expression:

$$\widehat{pr}_{ij} = \frac{1}{T} (\theta_a \cdot \hat{a}_{ij} + \theta_d \cdot \hat{d}_{ij} + \theta_g \cdot \hat{g}_{ij}). \quad (10)$$

where θ_a , θ_d and θ_g are constants controlling the contributions of directors, actors and genres to the rating predictions. Their values are estimated from a set of training data by finding the values that minimize Mean Average Error. Additionally, let T be the number of feature set ratings \hat{d}_{ij} , \hat{a}_{ij} and \hat{g}_{ij} that are different from 0. In the following sections, we will extend the \widehat{pr}_{ij} computation to include social-media feedback.

3.2 Social-Media Trends and Reputations

In this section, we formalize the social-media feedback,

$$S_j = \{T(m_j), reps(m_j)\}, \quad (11)$$

as the set of tweets $T(m_j)$ where the movie m_j is mentioned, and the reputation of all actors and directors participating on movie m_j .

New-movies popularity on Twitter

The social-media feedback about new movies is obtained from Twitter: tweets where the movie title is identified are stored and labelled according to the movie name. The captured tweets are then classified by a sentiment classifier such that, for each tweet, it is inferred if it is positive or negative reference to the movie. A tweets index is then constructed to allow fast look-ups for the cold-start recommendation. Formally, the resulting tweets for a certain movie m_j are represented as the set

$$T(m_j) = \{(t_{j1}, s_{j1}), \dots, (t_{jL}, s_{jL}), \dots, (t_{jM}, s_{jM})\}, \quad (12)$$

where t_{jl} is the tweet (talking about m_j) and s_{jl} is the sentiment of the tweet such that $s_{jl} \in \{pos, neg\}$. We used a k -nn classifier and a domain specific lexicon, see [12].

Actors and directors reputation on IMDb

The social-media feedback on directors and actors is obtained from IMDb: movie reviews are crawled and used to build a sentiment graph linking named-entities, from which the reputation of directors and actors is computed (see [12] for details). This step allows us to obtain the reputation of the directors and actors of the new movies we want to recommend. Formally, the reputation of all the directors and actors participating on movie m_j is represented by the expression

$$\text{reps}(m_j) = \{\text{rep}(e_1), \dots, \text{rep}(e_k), \dots\}, \quad (13)$$

where the reputation of each entity e_k is $\text{rep}(e_k) \in [0.0, 1.0]$, with 0.0 being the worst reputation and 1.0 being the best reputation.

3.3 Recommendations with Social-Media Signals

Moshfeghi et al. [8] and Krauss et al. [4] obtained hidden latent factors, to correlate movies through sentiment analysis. Here, however, new movies do not have reviews and tweets about new movies are too scarce to infer relevant latent topics. Therefore, we explore emotion as a qualitative measure, in which we obtain and consider the inherent quality of new movies, directors and actors.

The rating prediction \hat{r}_{ij} is obtained by considering both, how popular the movie is, $\text{pop}(m_j)$, and how much a user might enjoy the movie m_j , given the reputation $\text{reps}(m_j)$ of its participants. The proposed approach is formalized as

$$\hat{r}_{ij} = \alpha_t \cdot (\text{pop}(m_j) + \text{bias}_i) + (1 - \alpha_t) \cdot \widehat{pr}_{ij|\text{reps}(m_j)}, \quad (14)$$

where α_t is a constant reflecting the importance of the movies popularity to the final user-movie rating. Formally, the user u_i bias accounts for the deviation of the user ratings from the general average rating:

$$\text{bias}_i = \frac{\sum_{r_i^k \in ur_i} (r_i^k - \text{avg}_{\langle k \rangle})}{|ur_i|}. \quad (15)$$

Let $wr_i = \{r_i^1, \dots, r_i^k, \dots, r_i^K\}$ be the user u_i ratings, $avg_{<k>}$ be the average rating of the movie $m_{<k>}$, and $|wr_i|$ is the number of ratings given by user u_i . Rewriting eq. (10) with the new reputations information we have:

$$\widehat{pr}_{ij|\text{reps}(m_j)} = \frac{1}{T} \left(\theta_a \cdot \widehat{a}_{ij|\text{reps}(m_j)} + \theta_d \cdot \widehat{d}_{ij|\text{reps}(m_j)} + \theta_g \cdot \widehat{g}_{ij} \right). \quad (16)$$

Modeling user preferences $\widehat{a}_{ij|\text{reps}(m_j)}$ and $\widehat{d}_{ij|\text{reps}(m_j)}$ with social-media signals

Up until this point, when predicting the values \widehat{d}_{ij} and \widehat{a}_{ij} (i.e., how much a user likes or dislikes the directors and actors of a movie), the entities that the user does not know were not considered. In this section, we propose to enhance the calculation of \widehat{d}_{ij} and \widehat{a}_{ij} , given the reputations of directors and actors available in $\text{reps}(m_j)$. For this purpose, two new variables, \widehat{ud}_{ij} and \widehat{ua}_{ij} , are introduced to express the reputation of the unknown directors and actors:

$$\widehat{ud}_{ij} = \frac{\sum_{d \in D_j} \text{rep}(d)}{|D_j|}, \quad \widehat{ua}_{ij} = \frac{\sum_{a \in A_j} \text{rep}(a)}{|A_j|}, \quad (17)$$

where $D_j - D^i$ and $A_j - A^i$ are the sets of directors and actors on movie m_j that the user does not know.

To consider \widehat{ud}_{ij} and \widehat{ua}_{ij} , in the calculation of $\widehat{pr}_{ij|\text{reps}(m_j)}$, one ought to note that \widehat{d}_{ij} and \widehat{a}_{ij} represent user preferences towards their known directors and actors. Thus, $\widehat{d}_{ij|\text{reps}(m_j)} = \widehat{d}_{ij}$ and $\widehat{a}_{ij|\text{reps}(m_j)} = \widehat{a}_{ij}$, when all the directors or actors of m_j are known by the user, and $\widehat{d}_{ij|\text{reps}(m_j)} = \widehat{ud}_{ij}$ and $\widehat{a}_{ij|\text{reps}(m_j)} = \widehat{ua}_{ij}$, when the user does not know any directors or actors of the movie. The general case is when the user knows some of the directors and actors of the movie. Formally, the final directors and actors scores $\widehat{d}_{ij|\text{reps}(m_j)}$ and $\widehat{a}_{ij|\text{reps}(m_j)}$ are calculated by considering both the user preferences and the public opinion, i.e., a weighted average between the scores of the known entities and the unknown entities:

$$\widehat{d}_{ij|\text{reps}(m_j)} = \delta_{ud} \cdot (\widehat{ud}_{ij} + \text{bias}_i) + (1 - \delta_{ud}) \cdot \widehat{d}_{ij}, \quad (18)$$

$$\widehat{a}_{ij|\text{reps}(m_j)} = \delta_{ua} \cdot (\widehat{ua}_{ij} + \text{bias}_i) + (1 - \delta_{ua}) \cdot \widehat{a}_{ij}, \quad (19)$$

where the constants δ_{ud} and δ_{ua} , represent the contribution of the unknown directors and actors to the computation of \widehat{d}_{ij} and \widehat{a}_{ij} respectively. They are computed as:

$$\delta_{ud} = \frac{|D_j - D^i|}{|D_j|}, \quad \delta_{ua} = \frac{|A_j - A^i|}{|A_j|}, \quad (20)$$

where $|D_j - D^i|$ is the number of directors on movie m_j that the user u_i does not know and $|A_j - A^i|$ is the number of actors on movie m_j that the user does not know.

Modeling a movie popularity $\text{pop}(m_j)$ with social-media trends

So far, the predicted rating \widehat{pr}_{ij} captures an incomplete set of indicators about the movie, missing a key indicator which is the trendiness of that movie. Krauss et al. [4] has indeed showed that movie trendiness is projected in Oscar nominations, which are generally associated with highly rated movies. The set $T(m_j)$, containing tweets targeting movie m_j , can be used to predict its reputation. Oghina et al. [7] have shown that the

fraction of likes/dislikes is the strongest feature for predicting IMDb movie ratings from social-media. Following this remarks, we consider the popularity of a movie m_j , to be measured as

$$\text{pop}(m_j) = \frac{|pos_j|}{|tweets_j|}, \quad (21)$$

where $|pos_j|$ is the number of positive tweets referring the movie m_j and $|tweets_j|$ is the total number of tweets referring m_j .

4 Evaluation

4.1 Datasets

To set up a realistic evaluation scenario, we obtained our dataset by crawling IMDb user-movie ratings. We focused the extraction process on users who have rated at least one of a selection of 60 new movies, finalists on 5 popular movie awards ceremonies: the 2014 editions of *The Golden Globes*, *The Critic’s Choice Awards*, *The BAFTA Film Awards*, *The Independent Spirit Awards* and *The Oscars*. We selected such movies so we could capture a great number of tweets in a small time period. We also crawled 52,236 tweets, between January 2014 and March 2014, regarding the new movies.

In total, we obtained a dataset with 1,064,766 ratings, given by 2,909 users to 60 new movies and 46,843 old movies. The computation of the actors and directors reputation [12] for the new movies used a total of 124,236 IMDb reviews. In total we considered 225 actors and 169 directors corresponding to the 60 new movies. Finally, the movies metadata for all rated movies were obtained through the publicly available OMDb API (www.omdbapi.com).

4.2 Methods

To evaluate the proposed approach we leveraged on data concerning 60 new movies collected from different sources. This created a realistic setting to assess the different elements of the model formalized in eq. (14). The first method (MRep), assesses the contribution of the movie reputation $\text{pop}(m_j)$, which is inferred from tweets available through Twitter API. The second method (ERep), assesses the contribution of entities reputations $\hat{a}_{ij|\text{reps}(m_j)}$ and $\hat{d}_{ij|\text{reps}(m_j)}$, which were computed from IMDb reviews. The third method (FRep), uses the full spectrum of social-media reputation where both movies popularity and entities reputation are considered. We evaluate each variant by comparing the predicted ratings to the real user-movie ratings for the new movies. We use the Mean Average Error (MAE) to evaluate rating predictions and the F-Measure to evaluate recommendations.

The proposed approach, was also compared to baseline methods where recommendations are predicted from the movies metadata and past ratings. The first baseline is the k -nn algorithm which is widely successful for hybrid recommendations [11]. In the

k - nn algorithm a movie is represented by its average rating and a binary vector representing its metadata (a user is represented by its rated movies). The second baseline, formalized in eq. (10), does not include any social-media feedback: it is formal model where user ratings directly affect the importance of each aspect of a movie metadata. We distinguish the case where θ_d , θ_a and θ_g are all equal to 1.0 and where these weights were estimated with 10-fold cross validation, resulting in $\theta_d = 0.35$, $\theta_a = 0.2$ and $\theta_g = 0.45$. We refer to these models as FM1 and FM2, respectively.

Before discussing the main results, we evaluate Twitter as a source of reliable movie feedback. We also estimate the best δ_t parameter for eq. (21), relevant for Movie Reputation and Full Reputation, and discuss how the inclusion of user bias influences the results.

4.3 Results and Discussion

Twitter for Estimating a Movie Popularity. We use Twitter as a source of movie feedback to predict the reputation for new movies. We compare the predicted reputations with the average IMDb ratings of the target movies, captured several months after the movies’ release data. Fig. 1 shows the predicted ratings and the IMDb average ratings. From it, we can observe the overall deviation of the predicted ratings.

Fig. 1. Twitter-based Movie Ratings vs IMDb Movie Ratings.

Overall, the MAE is 0.59, which translates into very accurate results, considering that the rating scale is very ample (from 1 to 10). The prediction errors varied from 0.026 (*Blue is the Warmest Colour*) to 2.29 (*Her*). By analysing the overall error, we can observe that movies with lower IMDb ratings are more likely to have a higher prediction error: for instance, while *Blue is the Warmest Colour* has an average IMDb rating of 8.0, examples of high error such as *The Invisible Woman* (MAE=2.01) and *Computer Chess* (MAE=1.73), have an average IMDb rating of 6.3. This leads us to believe that Twitter users are more likely to share positive tweets about movies than negative tweets, which makes our method more precise for highly rated movies.

Estimation of the α_t parameter. In eq. (14), the parameter α_t controls the influence of the movie reputation in the user-movie rating predictions. In order to find the best value for α_t , we computed rating predictions for various α_t values on a validation dataset. Fig. 2 plots the MAE and F-Measure curves for a range of value. Both MRep and FRep present the best results for δ_t values below or equal to 0.40 – after this point both MAE and F-Measure start to deteriorate. For movie reputation, both the best MAE and F-Measure values are obtained at $\alpha_t = 0.35$ (MAE of 1.2266 and F-Measure of 87.2%). For full reputation, the best F-Measure is also obtained at 0.35 (87.7%), while the best MAE is obtained at 0.20. These results suggest that the general opinion about the movies, has a significant influence when predicting user-movie *cold-start* ratings. However, if the general opinion (α_t) is too contrary to the personal preferences, the predicted user-movie rating loses the personalization component, leading to less accurate predictions. For subsequent experiments, we set $\alpha_t = 0.35$.

Fig. 2. Estimation of δ_t as a function of Mean Absolute Error and F-Measure.

User-bias. User bias is considered in our methods to adjust the general opinions about movies, directors and actors to each user preferences. We predict user-movie ratings with the three main methods (MRep, ERep and FRep), both considering and not considering user bias ($bias_i = 0$). Table 2 presents the obtained MAE and F-Measure results for each method, both including and excluding user bias. As we can observe, the inclusion of user bias improves the results in all three approaches: the MAE decreases in all methods and the F-Measure increases. In terms of rating prediction, MRep presents the best results (1.227) and ERep presents the worst results (1.254), while FRep presents neither the best nor the worst result (1.245). These values suggest that the reputation of the movie itself is more useful for predicting the user-movie rating, when compared to the reputation of directors and actors.

When computing recommendations, assessed by F-Measure, FRep presents the best results (87.7%), when compared to MRep (87.2%) and ERep (85.9%). Unlike when predicting the user-movie rating, considering both the reputation of movies and the reputation of directors and actors is the best approach to distinguishing relevant movies from irrelevant movies. For subsequent experiments, we will consider user bias.

Table 1. The influence of user bias.

Methods	with bias		Without bias	
	MAE	F-M	MAE	F-M
MRep	1.227	87.2%	1.241	86.4%
ERep	1.254	85.9%	1.261	85.3%
FRep	1.245	87.7%	1.248	86.8%

Methods Comparison. Figures 3 shows the MAE and F-Measure results for users with different numbers of rated old movies. This enables us to compare how each method handles different levels of user sparsity. From all the methods, *k-nn* presents the worst results: it has the worst MAE for all levels of users; in recommendation, it only matches other methods for users with more than 40 rated movies. From the other baseline methods, FM2 presents better results than FM1 in both MAE and F-Measure for all values, suggesting that directors, actors and genres should weight differently when predicting user-movie ratings. The three main methods perform better than all baselines, both in rating prediction and recommendation. ERep performs better than MRep when recommending to users with less than 70 rated movies, while MRep performs better than ERep for users with a high number of rated movies. This shows that the reputation of a movie is only better to predict its ratings when accompanied with well-defined user preferences. FRep presents the best recommendation results overall: it performs very closely to ERep when recommending to users with less or equal to 70 rated movies and very closely to MRep when recommending for users with a lot of rated movies. Table 2 summarizes the overall results on all measures for all the methods, for all the dataset.

Fig. 3. Mean average error comparison.

Overall, all the methods that consider social-media information outperform the baselines. In terms of rating prediction, MRep presents the best MAE results. FRep, for instance, presents the best results in all recommendation measures, with a total F-Measure of 87.7%. The improvement in Recall values for the social-media methods relatively to the baselines shows that the reputation of movies, directors and actors help especially in identifying great movies, which are more usually relevant for users.

Table 2. Overall comparative results.

	MAE	Prec. (%)	Rec. (%)	F-M (%)
<i>k-nn</i>	1.3933	70.1	86.5	78.3
FM1	1.3058	70.3	85.2	77.8
FM2	1.2962	71.4	87.7	79.6
MRep	<u>1.2266</u>	<u>76.0</u>	98.5	87.2
ERep	1.2536	75.6	96.1	85.9
FRep	1.2450	<u>76.0</u>	<u>99.4</u>	<u>87.7</u>

Cases of extreme user cold-start. When users have not rated many movies, their preferences cannot be well modelled: these users suffer from the *cold-start* problem. This happens mostly, but not exclusively, for users who are new to the system. We simulate a scenario where all our 2,909 test users suffer from the *cold-start* problem by not considering their previous ratings and perform experiments with MRep, ERep and FRep. Table 3 show both the obtained MAE and F-Measure results for each method. Note that users bias cannot be considered in this scenario since there are no previously given ratings from any user.

Table 3. Extreme user-side cold-start.

	MAE	F-Measure
MRep	1.62	74.75%
ERep	1.77	63.50%
FRep	1.64	69.38%

ERep obtains the worst results (MAE of 1.7741 and F-Measure of 63.5%) while MRep obtains the best results (MAE of 1.6236 and F-Measure of 74.75%). FRep presents intermediate results. These results show that the reputation of movies is a good baseline predictor of the quality of a movie and is useful for recommending movies when the user preferences are not known. While the reputation of the movie directors and actors present much worse results, these also prove to be an average predictor of a movie quality, as a 63.5% recommendation accuracy is very good for a scenario where there is no information on users.

5 Conclusion

This paper addressed the problem of recommending new movies, affected by the cold-start problem, by monitoring information from social-media services. More specifically, it focused on exploring how the reputation of movies, directors and actors can be used to tackle this issue. Our experiments have shown that Twitter is a reliable source for predicting reputation of new movies: we were able to predict the actual IMDb average rating with a Mean Average Error (MAE) value of 0.59, in a rating scale from 1 to 10. In turn, the reputations of new movies, directors and actors have proven to be

useful in cases of movie-side cold-start: we were able to improve recommendation by 8.1% when compared to our baseline method, reaching an F-Measure value of 87.7%.

Finally, the proposed framework has also shown to be useful in severe cases of both movie-side and user-side cold-start: we were able to recommend movies with an F-Measure of 74.75%. This is a major improvement over the baseline methods, where it would be not possible to recommend movies in this scenario.

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